
THE DISTINCTION BETWEEN “WORD” AND “TERM”

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Abstract: This article explores the evolution and theoretical underpinnings of terminology as a field of study, tracing its roots to the need for standardization and coherence in professional communication among experts. Through an examination of key concepts and definitions, including the distinction between 'word' and 'term,' the article highlights the interdisciplinary nature of terminology and its intersections with fields such as Philosophy, Sociology, Cognitive Science, and Linguistics.

Key words: terminology, specialized language, science, technology, communication.

Terminology or specialized language is more than a technical or particular instance of general language. In today's society with its emphasis on science and technology, the way specialized knowledge concepts are named, structured, described, and translated has put terminology or the designation of specialized knowledge concepts in the limelight. The information in scientific and technical texts is encoded in terms or specialized knowledge units, which are access points to more complex knowledge structures.

Terminology emerged as a field of study relatively recently, driven by the increasing necessity to facilitate specialized communication, translation, and knowledge transfer among individuals from different language communities with similar expertise levels. Theoretical developments in terminology have predominantly focused on practical applications, emphasizing the creation of glossaries, specialized dictionaries, and resources for terminology and translation. According to Cabri (2000, 37), terminology arises from the need of technicians and scientists to standardize concepts and terms within their respective fields, thus enhancing professional communication and knowledge exchange.

Consequently, terminology has long sought a theoretical framework capable of explaining specialized knowledge representation, category organization, and description, as well as the semantic and syntactic behavior of terminological units across various languages. This quest has prompted terminologists to consider whether terminology should be classified as a branch of Philosophy, Sociology, Cognitive Science, Linguistics, or other related disciplines.

Terminology serves the crucial function of establishing a precise link between a term and its corresponding concept, with the term already existing within the

specialized language. Jennifer Pearson distinguishes between two types of terminologists: "Traditional Terminologists," who analyze terms in isolation without considering their context, and "Modern Terminologists," who assess usage to determine meaning, taking into account textual variations (Pearson, 1998). Pearson notes that both traditional and modern terminologists share a common perspective rooted in the theoretical framework developed by Eugen Wüster in the early 20th century (Pearson, 1998, p. 2).

A term can be understood as a word comprised of linguistic elements and systems. It serves as a sign closely associated with a specialized conceptual content. In contemporary times, the notion of 'systematic terminology' is grounded in the principles of science, representing a well-structured language system (Popp, 2001). According to the dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics, a term is defined as "a unit of expression that is universally recognized by native speakers in both spoken and written language." However, the dictionary acknowledges the limitations of conventional definitions, such as "units of meaning" or "idea," due to their inherent vagueness. Terms can manifest orthographically in written form and phonologically in spoken language (Crystal, 2008).

An influential definition proposed by Bloomfield describes a term as a "minimal free form," denoting the smallest unit capable of constituting a complete utterance (Crystal, 2008). Jennifer Pearson, drawing from the perspective of traditional terminologists, defines a term as "labels for concepts that are abstract entities isolated from text." These terms, which are collectively agreed upon, can consist of either a single word or a multiword unit.

The fundamental distinction between a term and a word lies in their respective nature of reference. A term is characterized by its mono-referential quality, representing a highly specific concept within a particular area, field, or discipline. Unlike words, which may encompass various meanings and contexts, terms in mining terminology are intricately linked to their specialized domain, imposing linguistic (lexical, syntactical, and semantic) as well as conceptual (generic, portative, and casual) constraints. For instance, in the mining industry, the term "**tailings**" specifically refers to the byproducts of ore extraction and processing, whereas the word "**waste**" may have broader applications across different industries. The term "**stripping ratio**" specifically refers to the ratio of overburden (non-valuable material covering an ore body) to ore in an open-pit mining operation. This term is crucial for determining the economic feasibility of mining projects and optimizing resource extraction processes. Unlike the word "**ratio**", which can have various interpretations in different contexts, "stripping ratio" is narrowly defined within the specialized domain of mining engineering, highlighting its mono-referential nature.

This distinction illustrates how terms in mining terminology serve as precise linguistic tools to convey specialized meanings within the context of resource extraction and processing.

Scholars working in the field of terminology mentioned the kinds of terminology:

- Classical terminology: in which terms must be univocal (monosemous), its value defined by external, non-linguistic reference points.

- Descriptive terminology: Terms can be called the special use of polysemous words defined in the dictionaries.

- Socio-cognitive terminology: it discusses the cognitive aspect of terminology in domain-specific language related to verbal, situational and cognitive contexts of various discourses.

Underlying the information in the text are entire conceptual domains, which are both explicitly and implicitly present, and which represent the specialized knowledge encoded. In order to create a specialized text, translators and technical writers must have an excellent grasp of the language in the conceptual domain, the content that must be transmitted, and the knowledge level of the addressees or text receivers. In order to translate a specialized language text, translators must go beyond correspondences at the level of individual terms, and be able to establish interlinguistic references to entire knowledge structures. Only then can they achieve the level of understanding necessary to create an equivalent text in the target language.

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The distinction between 'word' and 'term' is foundational to understanding the intricacies of specialized language, particularly in the realms of science and technology. Terminology, often regarded as a specialized language in its own right, plays a pivotal role in how knowledge concepts are named, structured, described, and translated within today's society.

As we've explored, terminology emerged as a discipline in response to the growing need for effective communication and translation among individuals from diverse language communities with similar levels of expertise. Theoretical frameworks in terminology have predominantly focused on practical applications, such as the

development of glossaries, specialized dictionaries, and terminological resources, aimed at facilitating professional communication and knowledge transfer.

Central to the study of terminology is the distinction between 'word' and 'term.' While a word may encompass a broad range of meanings and contexts, a term is a linguistic unit closely linked to a specific conceptual content within a specialized domain. This distinction is essential for ensuring precision and clarity in communication, particularly within technical and scientific fields where accuracy is paramount.

Terminology extends beyond mere linguistic considerations to encompass broader conceptual domains, representing the specialized knowledge encoded within a given field. Translators and technical writers tasked with translating specialized texts must possess not only linguistic proficiency but also a deep understanding of the conceptual domain and the intended audience's knowledge level. This necessitates the establishment of interlinguistic references to entire knowledge structures, enabling the creation of equivalent texts in target languages.

The study of terminology underscores the importance of precision, clarity, and coherence in specialized communication. By recognizing the distinction between 'word' and 'term' and understanding the broader conceptual domains underlying specialized knowledge, we can navigate the complexities of technical and scientific discourse with greater efficacy and precision. Terminology, therefore, stands as a cornerstone of effective communication and knowledge dissemination in today's increasingly interconnected world.

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